

School Library Management: A Literature Review

Alifa Soraya Nuryadika¹, Hasan Hariri²

¹Student of Education Administration, Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

²Lecturer of Education Administration, Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This article aims to find out how school libraries is managed based on the literature review from previous research from several countries around the world. This article uses search and review methods, where the review process began with a search engine, Google scholar and IEEE, to search the articles with keywords. The authors found the scope of the reviewed articles was still very limited so it needs to be followed up related to school turnover management research. Result of the review show that libraries can run optimally if they apply good management. The research about this topic is limited and this article is a literature review; so further research needs to be done related to school library management in general and to include other data collection methods including interview and questionnaire. The theoretical benefit of this article is to add knowledge about educational library management and the practical benefit is as an information for further research.

KEYWORDS: Management, Library, Education, School, Administration

1. INTRODUCTION

The library is one of the learning tools that can be a force to educate the nation. The library has an important role as a bridge to the mastery of science as well as a place of recreation that is fun and refreshing. Libraries make an important contribution to the opening of information about science (Siregar, 2017).

In its administration, the library requires its own space along with various accessories. The more complete the equipment, the more it supports the implementation of the school library. The available space and equipment must be arranged and maintained properly so that it can support the effective and efficient operation of the school library (Azwar & Rusli, 2016).

The library must be able to become an alternative center for teaching and learning activities and reading centers to increase knowledge and recreation. The school library is expected to not only provide reading books but also to provide other sources of information such as audiovisual and multimedia materials, as well as to access information on the internet. In the teaching and learning process, books have a very important role because books are sources of information (Novyanti, Dahrani, Padli, & Maharani, 2019). Lasa revealed that there are several important functions of the school library, including as an educational medium, for learning, for conducting simple research, as an application of information technology in experts and as an alternative to the development of classroom knowledge and sources of information (Siagian, Siregar, & Nasution, 2019). Another function of the library is to play an important role to fulfill all information needed by the community members in an educational institution (Williment, 2019).

Libraries as educational institutions and institutions information provider will have good performance if libraries are supported by adequate management, so that all activities of the institution will lead to effort to achieve the goals that have been set. The library as a source of learning that has a big influence in the world of education, one of the roles of the school library is to improve student learning outcomes or achievements. Because with the library it is expected that students can develop skills to find information for their needs independently. This is of course by using the library as much as possible using good management (Marlina & Suandi, 2019).

In general, many problems faced by library staff in library management. The problem that often arises in library management are in terms of funding management and the lack of prioritized focus, both from the government or internal institutions because of the flow of information. This has resulted in some libraries that are still less in demand by millennial young people who prefer to access reading material through smart phones. This can also be seen from a number of phenomena that occur, among others, the low percentage of the budget allocated to libraries, the low planning of library development programs, implementation and evaluation, the lack of government efforts to find library funding and the weak efforts to integrate library services with school curriculum (Hermawan & Prayoga, 2020).

Library management in every educational institution will face a big challenge in evaluating its performance because many cases of this assessment are done incorrectly. One challenge is the lack of a fair approach to reallocate resources in the library system at school (Bernardo, de Souza, Lopes, & Rodrigues, 2020) this happened due to several issues regarding library management in schools. First, the majority of school libraries are managed by individuals who have no training or background in library management and librarians in general. The need to find qualified personnel for the library is a core problem in the future. Second, lack of support from administrators or principals. School administrators determine the quality of school library media programs as do librarians because they influence or control libraries and librarians under their supervision. Third, funding support. Library budgets are always at stake and most are not prioritized in budget allocations or allocations.

There are issues related to library management in schools. To be able to answer these issues, a literature review will be conducted on.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Management

According to Lasa Hs, et al., management is an applied science that can be utilized by various organizations, institutions, including libraries to help managers / heads to solve various problems in one organization / library (Putri & Maralis, 2019).

George R Terry in his book titled "Principle of Management" provides a definition: "Management is a process that distinguishes between planning, organizing, driving implementation, and supervision, by utilizing both science and art, in order to be able to complete the goals set previously (Putra & Nugroho, 2019).

Management is an activity to manage an organization so that the organization achieves its goals. In realizing organizational goals, management emphasizes the use of resources effectively and efficiently. Effective relating to carrying out a job with the correct procedures for achieving goals. So, management is a scientific discipline related to governance, managing things so that they become good and in accordance with the direction of the goals and principles of regular implementation (Yuliana, Sri, & Son, 2019).

Management activities are activities that reflect the existence of a system, which consists of several aspects or factors to support it (Zohriah, 2018). Management practices that have been applied by principals are drawing a lot of attention, because during the last decade with the introduction of new regulations, schools and the principal has become more independent in a number of fields, including having his own wisdom educational programs, organizing their own activities and introducing innovative teaching methods and initiatives. That the heterogeneity that resulted in potential management practices affect differences between schools in terms of learning outcomes (Yeh & Walter, 2016).

School library management is not just an activity of placing books on the shelves, but more than that, it is very complex, sustainable, and always changes. Management is a process of focusing and paying attention to activities in the library from day to day, dealing with content problems and integration with school goals. Management activities are activities that reflect the existence of a system, related and consists of several aspects or factors to support it (Ayunitias, Fatimah, & Rusmin, 2019).

So management can be interpreted as an action to achieve goals through the efforts of other people. In relation to school libraries, school library management is basically the process of optimizing human, material, and budget contributions to achieve library goals. Because the school library as a sub-system of an organization, in this case is the school, of course the purpose of the school library must be clearly defined first. From management it can be done in the form of programs that will be implemented along with concrete and operational targets. To achieve the specified goals, then the school library management activities can be implemented or realized (Rokan, 2017).

Library management system is a computerized process for processing library data, starting from cataloging collections, processing data of members, to the process of borrowing and returning collections and their rules in an integrated manner (Saputra, 2018).

So to manage a library, good management skills are required, so that the direction of activities is in accordance with the desired goals. The ability of management is also needed to maintain the balance of different goals and be able to be carried out effectively and efficiently. Basic knowledge in managing a library so that it runs well is management science, because management is needed in various lives to regulate the steps that must be carried out by all elements in a library. Therefore, in the management process, it is necessary to have a planning process, organizing, leadership, and controlling. In addition, management is also intended so that the elements involved in the library are able to do their jobs and work properly (Amidasti, 2019).

B. School Library

The library is a conducive space for creating and representing campus culture or community-safe intellectual space (Everett, 2018). The library is divided into three, academic, general, and special library groups (Raghu & Mothukuri, 2017).

According to Darmono, the library was used as a place for a collection of books or books to be organized as a medium for the learning process of the students (Almas, 2017). The definition of library was stated by Soedjono Trimono who said that the library was used as a place where all human knowledge or ideas were collected, both in print and in other forms (Suhardi, 2011). In supporting this role, libraries need to provide resources, facilities and services that will enable students to fulfill their academic potential. To carry out these activities, libraries constantly need to reassess their services to ensure they meet the needs of all reading interests (Harshani, Khatibi, & Azam, 2020).

School library is also called the heart of the education program or the term heart of the education program. For this reason, it is hoped that the library can be utilized as optimal as possible in supporting students' teaching and learning activities. Darmono said the library was needed in educational institutions because the school library was a source of learning in the school environment, the school library was one component of the approved system, the school library was a source to support the quality of education and further, the school library as a learning laboratory that enabled students to sharpen and enlarge the ability to read, write, think and speak (Fitria, 2018).

Based on the results of survivors conducted by Niels Ole Pors and Carl Gustav Johannsen showed that modern libraries must implement leadership and management accordingly. Management and leadership tend to be used to emphasize the importance of democratic values such as tolerance, dialogue, cooperation, motivation, mutual respect and distance themselves from rules and regulations, govern and control (Pors & Johannsen, 2003).

The integrated library system supports all academic library operations from obtaining and processing library resources to make them available to the user community and preserving it for future use. As library needs to develop, there is an urgent demand for libraries to migrate from one generation of ILS to the next generation. This complex migration process often requires significant financial and personnel investment but its success is not guaranteed at all (Yeh & Walter, 2016).

Therefore, the importance of libraries cannot be ignored in academic activities the student. By providing access to necessary information and intellectual resources, the library can greatly influence student learning process and overall academic performance. Thus, the library takes an important role in facilitating students towards education and help them in their academic career (Jan & Anwar, 2019).

Given the importance of school libraries, the Indonesian government is looking for the development of school libraries in Indonesia. The Indonesian government has set it in Law No. 43 of 2007 Article 23 concerning School Libraries, states that schools or madrassas (Islamic Schools) must regulate libraries within the National Education Standards (Harisanti & Grace, 2018).

In general, a library is an educational facility as a resource to facilitate teaching, learning and research. At the elementary school level, the class library should be designed to provide the learning resources needed by the teachers to improve student curriculum learning outcomes. Specifically, libraries must be able to:

- a. Give students quick access to resources to develop their interest in extensive reading to foster sustainable reading habits.
- b. Provide opportunities for students to use books and other learning materials to develop desired social, moral, and religious values.
- c. Making students develop aesthetic values and appreciate books and material information as a key to learn and develop (Omigie & Idiedo, 2019).

Managerial ability in managing the library is in line with the desire to realize a school library as mentioned above, of course there must be synergistic cooperation between librarians, teachers, principals, and school committees. In addition, there is also a need for positive appreciation of the existence of the library of all related components.

School library as one of the learning resource centers has a role as a means of educational media together with other educational elements in the implementation of teaching and learning processes. School library is a library that is held in schools to support teaching and learning programs in formal education institutions at the school level both elementary and secondary schools, both public schools and private schools. In simple terms, it can be said that the main task of a library is to collect library materials from the past, present and store and provide for the needs of current and future library users. From these functions, it can be seen that the school library should be an integral part of the learning system, as a complementary tool for the existence of schools, and the tastes

of the readers who in this case are students. The main function of the school library is to convey information contained in user collections, to be able to fulfill that function, information must be able to be sought or recovered (Algifarie & Suyatno, 2019)

The library as an educational institutions and information providers will have good performance if supported by adequate management, so that all the activities of the institution will lead to achieve the goals that have been planned. The library is a place to store and obtain information from various types of libraries. Library will be used as a tool for completing education in achieving educational goals, the existence of libraries in tertiary institutions is very important. To manage a library requires good management skills so that the direction of activities is according to the desired goals. Management capability is also needed to maintain a balance of different goals and to make it able to be carried out effectively and efficiently (Masdul & Rahmawati, 2019).

The school library is part of the facilities contained in the school environment and is fully managed by the school to assist the school in achieving its educational goals. There are several important functions of the school library, including as an educational medium, for learning, for conducting simple research, as an application of information technology in the transfer and development of science as an alternative class and source of information. So that it can be understood that the purpose of the school library is as a forum that provides a variety of knowledge through a collection of books that fit the needs of students so that students can develop talent, explore the world, and make the school library as a source of information (Siagian et al., 2019)

Knowledge about the library, a library manager should also be able to manage the library properly. The management includes the preparation of work programs and development programs, carrying out programs such as arrangement of facilities and equipment, procurement of collections, processing, circulation, services, and coaching, as well as carrying out supervision. Not just sitting still, or even rarely opening a library (Suhaemin & Arikunto, 2013). Besides that, school library management must be done professionally. Managers have to seriously carry out its activities in order to achieve progress and learning process in schools (Kamulyan & Primasari, 2016). The library can be used as an alternative center for teaching and learning activities and reading centers to increase knowledge for students. The school library is expected to not only provide reading books but also to provide other sources of information such as audiovisual and multimedia materials, as well as access the information on the internet. Management in the school library is not just an activity of placing books on a shelf, but more than that, it is very complex, sustainable and always changes (Novyanti et al., 2019).

The success of school libraries in organizing good learning resource services is indeed more focused on structuring and managing their work, but in the implementation of a good school library must provide adequate services and facilities. Services that ideally exist in the school library include the following: 1) library building or space, 2) library equipment and supplies, 3) library space layout, 4) collection of library materials, 5) librarian, 6) library services, 7) library rules (Muspawi & Piana, 2018).

The school library as an integral part of the school, the main component of education in schools, is expected to be able to support the achievement of learning objectives in schools. In line with this, Andi Prastowo stated that, the objectives of the school library were as follows: (a) encouraging and accelerating the process of mastering the reading techniques of students; (b) helps creative writing for students; (c) fostering interests and reading habits; (d) provide various kinds of information for the sake of curriculum implementation; (e) encourage, excite the spirit of reading and learning; (f) expand, deepen, and enrich student learning experiences by reading books and other collections; and (g) provide healthy entertainment to fill leisure time through reading activities, especially books and other creative reading sources (Badrudin, 2019).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This literature review focuses on library management in schools.

A. Search and Review Methods

The review process began with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with keywords. "School Management and Library". The search ranged from 2003-2020 and identified a total of 150 studies and articles. The criteria for inclusion in this study are as follows:

- a. Qualitative results from library management in schools.
- b. Research carried out in the world.
- c. The research uses English.
- d. Dissertations and theses are excluded.

Steps in the literature review of each of the school library management include:

Step 1: Formulate the Problem

- Choose a topic that fits the issue and interest.
- The problem must be written completely and accurately

Step 2: Look for Literature

- Look for literature relevant to research
- Get an overview of the research topic
- Research sources are very helpful if supported by knowledge of the topic being studied.
- These sources provide an overview / summary of the previous research.

Step 3: Evaluate Data

- Look at any contribution to the topic discussed
- Search and find the right data source as needed to support research
- It can be in the form of qualitative data, quantitative data or data derived from a combination of both

Step 4: Analysis and Interpretation

Step 5: Discuss and find and summarize literature.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section reports the main findings reviewed from several articles the author has read. The analysis selected most of the articles based on the benefits and management of the school library. The articles that have been reviewed are research conducted in several countries in the world. The table describes the results of the literature review conducted by the author. Research has been carried out in several schools and universities.

Table: School Library Management

Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Results
Pors and Johannsen (2003)	Library directors under crosspressure between new public management and value-based management	Denmark	Quantitative	Library leaders tend to view the role of the future as being people-oriented and towards values and see themselves as a kind of catalyst for change.
Swee and Abdullah (2005)	The Status Of School Library Automation In Malaysian Chinese Secondary Schools: A National Survey	Malaysia	Quantitative	Circulation is a function that is largely automated by libraries, followed by catalogs. The turnkey system is the choice for most automatic NTSS libraries, while the ICSS library chooses a system developed at home.
Karplus (2006)	Integrating Academic Library Resources and Learning Management Systems: The Library Blackboard Site	-	Literature review	A library Blackboard site provides tutorials, information, and links in a pedagogically viable format that can be accessed by the entire campus community anytime, anywhere. The site can be the focal point for many librarians in one location thus ensuring a consistent, collaborative instructional program.

Azwar and Rusli (2016)	Manajemen Tata Ruang Perpustakaan Pesantren Madani Alauddin Pao-Pao Makassar (Spatial Management of Madani Islamic Boarding School Library Alauddin Pao-Pao Makassar)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Madani Alauddin Pao-Pao Islamic Boarding School is still under construction or development so that the room has not been too many and the impact is the library users cannot enjoy library services properly.
De Bem and Dandolini (2016)	Knowledge Management Framework for University Libraries	Brazil	Qualitative	After evaluation, the management framework in the university library has been proved easy to be applied in the context of its creation (university library).
Yeh and Walter (2016)	Critical Success Factors for Integrated Library System Implementation in Academic Libraries: A Qualitative Study	United States of America	Qualitative	The integrated library system (ILS) supports all academic library business operations from obtaining and processing library resources to make them available to the user community and preserve them for future use.
Siregar (2017)	Implementasi Manajemen Perpustakaan Berbasis Teknologi untuk Percepatan Pelayanan (Implementation of Technology-Based Library Management for The Acceleration of Service)	Indonesia	Literature review	The strategy should be applied that is understanding the need for service quality improvement, service quality improvement, making alternative solutions to problem solving, deeply studied and decided the relevant solutions, studying the results of the solution, then the results will be known and set the standard for the pursued solution.
Raghu and Anjaiah (2017)	Best Library Practices in Business Schools of Hyderabad: A Case Study of VJIM	India	Quantitative	Web 2.0 is used as part of best practices for innovative methods used for library services.
Everett (2018)	Visualizing the Silent Dialogue About Race: Diversity Outreach in an Academic Library	United States of America	Quantitative and qualitative	Utilizing libraries as a safe space (intellectual) provides opportunities for students to learn about diversity and inclusion, and platforms for building collaborative campus relationships and increasing library visibility.
Fitria (2018)	Pemanfaatan Perpustakaan Sekolah Oleh Siswa di Sekolah Dasar Negeri Golo Yogyakarta (Utilization of School Libraries by Students in Golo Yogyakarta Elementary School)	Indonesia	Qualitative	1) Utilization of collections by reading and borrowing. 2) Factors that influence the use of school libraries for students, namely the needs, motivation, and the types of collection. Librarian efforts in optimizing libraries by holding a number of programs. 4) There are supporting and inhibiting factors to optimize the library.

Harisanti and Anugrah (2018)	Characteristics of Senior High School Students in the Utilization of School Libraries in Indonesia	Indonesia	Quantitative	Students visit the library more often during breaks compared to other times. Students use the library to do the school tasks and some students do other activities in the library. In terms of borrowing books, students mostly only borrow one book. Many collections do not fit between bookshelves and catalogs / OPAC.
Omigie and Idiedo (2019)	Developing Classroom Libraries for Promoting Primary Education in Nigeria	Nigeria	Qualitative	Class library as a resource for children in Nigerian schools will make teaching and learning very interesting and amazing by using mobile library technology tools to face the information age.
Putra and Nugroho (2019)	Manajemen Perpustakaan dalam Meningkatkan Minat Baca Peserta Didik (Library Management in Improving Student Interest in Reading)	Indonesia	Qualitative	1) Provision of library materials that can fulfill library functions; 2) improve library services; 3) introduce and guide them to be fond of and make them want to read the books; 4) working with class teachers; 5) motivate students' interest in reading by holding book fairs; 6) make a clipping from a newspaper, magazine, or bulletin; 7) compile a collection of books with a neat system; and 8) making loan administration.
Harshani, Khatibi, and Azam (2019)	Evaluating the Effect of Academic Library users' Experience towards Library Patronage in State Universities in Sri Lanka: Development of a Conceptual Framework	Sri Lanka	Quantitative	UX library professionals include librarians and library staff members who specialize in upgrading their library management through research and design.
Williment (2019)	It Takes a Community to Create a Library	Canada	Qualitative	The Community-Based Service Planning Model, shows that libraries can successfully implement this model to increase inclusiveness, and to guide students in achieving social goals, the ideals of the institution, and potency.
Jan and Anwar (2019)	Emotional Intelligence, Library Use and Academic Achievements of University Students	Pakistan	Quantitative	Students with relatively higher emotional intelligence scores often visit their university library. A significant positive relationship was found between emotional intelligence and academic achievement (GPA) of this student.

Bernardo, de Souza, Lopes, and Rodrigues (2020)	University Library Performance Management: Applying Zero-Sum Gains DEA Models to Resource Allocation	Brazil	Qualitative	The use of the ZSG model has been proved appropriate for the allocation of resources within library systems since it has improved overall efficiency achieved by the library redistribution. The staff advice is very attracted to the central management of the library system, because it allows the use of resources efficiently. As such, these results are very valuable for the reallocation of university library resources because it can represent management based on technical criteria and it reflects a fair allocation.
Hemawan and Prayoga (2020)	Implementasi Pengelolaan Perpustakaan di Madrasah Swasta (Implementation of Library Management in Private Madrasa)	Indonesia	Qualitative	Planning is carried out with the madrasa head at the madrasa level meeting by submitting a work program and submitting a draft budget (RAB), the program implementation at the library is carried out by the head of the library, namely borrowing books, daily library services, work program socialization, and supervision is carried out incidentally monthly and weekly.

Research studies on library management in schools have been carried out in various countries. Table shows that research studies have been carried out in schools and universities. Based on the results of literature reviews and reviews from sources obtained, the analysis shows that the library is an important component in an educational program. This means that the library is needed in schools to be able to support teaching and learning activities.

The writer will present findings that show that libraries are needed in schools to be able to support teaching and learning activities, this is in accordance with Stephanie Everett's research results showing that utilizing libraries as safe spaces (intellectuals) provides opportunities for students to learn about diversity and inclusion, and a platform for building relationships between collaborative educational institutions and increasing library visibility (Everett, 2018). The premise of this article is to find out how school library management is.

The development of the library from time to time shows that the library is a developing organism. The development of a library is inseparable from the development of library science. In this digital era, the progress and development of a library goes hand in hand with leadership that is able to create a quality organizational and communication culture that supports the achievement of library organization goals. Library organization requires a leader who can utilize well information technology and have sufficient productivity and characteristics in leading the organization. Library as a science provides various perspectives for each individual to study and analyze the peculiarities of the science. In managing a library, good management skills are needed so that all activities is in accordance with the stated goals. Management skills must be possessed by a library leader. He must know the direction, priorities, and goals of the organization at any given time. This is because the more advanced the technology, the more it is possible for libraries to more quickly convey their collections to users. Providing open collections and information to the public is a breakthrough that must be applied by every library. Information is basically a form of human expression in the form of facts and ideas that can be used. Delivering information and obtaining information are the rights of every individual that should not be limited by signs.

Based on the literature by the author shows that the library is not only new in the community, libraries have been held everywhere, such as in schools, both public schools and private schools, both elementary and high schools. Likewise in offices, even now public

libraries are being promoted both at the city and district levels up to the village level. By definition, school libraries are libraries within school educational institutions, which are integral part of the school concerned and sources of learning to support the achievement of the educational goals of the school concerned. The existence of the school library is not only limited to collect and store library materials, but also to assist students in getting the desired learning materials. As for the teacher, the library becomes the main reference source for obtaining subject matter.

The above explanation is in accordance with the results of Tee Lay Swee's research, Abrizah Abdullah revealed that revealed that the current school library is no longer a traditional reading room and study room; they evolved to become information service facilitators and a gateway to the wider world of information (Swee & Abdullah, 2005). Utilization of collections in libraries can be read and borrowed by users to support learning. There are factors that influence the use of school libraries for students, namely the needs, motivation, and type of collection. For this reason, librarians need to work to optimize the library by holding a number of programs. It must be noted that there are supporting and inhibiting factors in efforts to optimize the library.

The library can be utilized as a safe space (intellectual) providing opportunities for students to learn about diversity and inclusion, and platforms for building collaborative campus relationships and increasing library visibility. Students visit the library more often during breaks compared to other times. Students use the library for school work and some students do other activities in the library. In terms of borrowing books, students mostly only borrow one book. Many collections do not fit between bookshelves and catalogs / OPAC.

The academic library focuses on aspects of information literacy resources. Catalog consortium, inter-library loans. and document delivery has expanded the material available to users. Inter library services have begun to join commercial online, web-based products. The new interface and software capabilities have been busy with technical services (Karplus, 2017).

Utilization of collections in libraries can be read and borrowed by the users to support learning. There are factors that influence the use of school libraries for students, namely the needs, motivation, and the types of collection. For this reason, librarians need to work to optimize the library by holding a number of programs. It must be noted that there are supporting and inhibiting factors to optimize the library.

Class library resources for children in schools can make teaching and learning very interesting and amazing by using mobile library technology tools to face the information age. Libraries can take advantage of library automation applications, these applications can support operational activities in school libraries which include circulation activities, the collection of collections into the database and data collection of library members. In addition, web 2.0 is used as part of best practices for innovative methods used for library services.

Library leaders tend to view the role of the future as being very people-oriented and towards values and see themselves as a kind of catalyst for change. This is consistent with the results of studies that students with relatively higher emotional intelligence scores often visit their university library. A significant positive relationship was found between emotional intelligence and academic achievement (GPA) of this student. Management in the library can be characterized as an innate activity, because the library has a basis for gaining knowledge and sharing information. However, there are several frameworks that have characteristics that enable implementation of a library management (De Bem, Coelho, & Dandolini, 2016).

Management in the library can be characterized as an innate activity, because the library has a basis for gaining knowledge and sharing information. Libraries will not run well if they are not supported by management. Libraries will not achieve their vision and mission if they are not accompanied by management. However, there are several frameworks that have characteristics that enable implementation of a library management. This review has limitations including; first, the articles are reviewed only in English so other studies are not reviewed because of the limitations. Second, dissertations and these are not discussed in this article because they can cause publication bias in the results. Third, the scope of the articles reviewed is still very limited, and it is very difficult to get literature. Further discussion is needed due to the difficulty of finding literature.

5. CONCLUSION

This article aims to see how school libraries are managed based on literature reviews from previous research. Most of the literature review results show that it is difficult to obtain literature related to management of libraries. So the authors will explain the findings that show that libraries are needed in schools to support teaching and learning activities. The school library is no longer a traditional reading and study room; they develop into information service facilitators and a gateway to a wider world of information. This

review has some limitations, including; First, articles are reviewed in English only so other studios are not reviewed due to limitations. Second, the dissertation and thesis are not discussed in this article as they may cause publication bias in the results. Third, the coverage of the articles review is still limited, and it is very difficult to find the literature. Further discussion is needed because of the difficulty of finding literature.

In general, the library is an educational facility to facilitate the teaching and learning process and research. Research is a storehouse of knowledge because it can provide new knowledge. The school library is also called the heart of the educational program. Libraries can help students in schools to improve their performance. The purpose of the library is to help students achieve the specific goals of the school concerned and educational goals in general. Therefore, the library is expected to be used as much as possible in supporting student teaching and learning activities. Therefore, the importance of libraries cannot be ignored in student academic activities. By providing access to the information and intellectual resources needed, libraries can greatly influence student learning and overall academic performance.

Libraries are educational institutions and information providers, have good performance if supported by adequate management, so that all institutional activities will lead to efforts to achieve the goals that have been planned. Libraries in educational and information institutions will work best if they are supported by adequate management. The management of all these activities will lead to predetermined goals, so that all elements will try to work in accordance with the needs of the library. Management is indispensable in many lives to organize the steps that must be carried out by all elements in a library. Good management is needed, so that the direction of activities is in accordance with the desired goals. Libraries cannot run well if they do not implement good management. Libraries will not succeed in satisfying users with their information services and all information sources owned by libraries if they are not supported by management. Libraries will not achieve their roles and functions if they do not involve management in their implementation. Several management principles need to be applied, namely planning, structuring, implementing, and controlling necessary for the library to run well. Good management will optimize the function of the library which is expected to be one of the components that improve students' academics. Service is one of the supporting elements of library management.

REFERENCES

1. Algifarie, A. D., & Suyatno, S. (2019). Pemanfaatan perpustakaan sekolah di sd muhammadiyah wirobrajan 3 yogyakarta. *Jurnal Fundadikdas (Fundamental Pendidikan Dasar)*, 2(2), 51-57.
2. Almas, H. (2017). Manajemen sistem informasi di perpustakaan smk negeri 3 malang. *Bibliotika: Jurnal Kajian Perpustakaan dan Informasi*, 1(1). doi:10.17977/um008v1i12017p091
3. Amidasti, D. (2019). Hubungan manajemen perpustakaan dan minat baca dengan prestasi mahasiswa di sekolah tinggi ilmu ekonomi indragiri (stie-i) rengat tahun akademik 2018-2019. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 8(1), 189-199. doi:10.34006/jmbi.v8i1.69
4. Ayunitias, E., Fatimah, S., & Rusmin, A. (2019). Pengaruh manajemen perpustakaan sekolah terhadap minat baca peserta didik pada mata pelajaran ekonomi di sma negeri 1 indralaya utara. *Jurnal PROFIT Kajian Pendidikan Ekonomi dan Ilmu Ekonomi*, 6(1). Retrieved from <https://ejournal.unsri.ac.id/index.php/jp/article/view/7874>.
5. Azwar, M., & Rusli, A. N. (2016). Manajemen tata ruang perpustakaan pesantren madani alauddin pao-pao makassar. *AL-MAKTABAH*, 15(1). Retrieved from <http://journal.uinjkt.ac.id/index.php/al-maktabah/article/viewFile/4714/3245>.
6. Badrudin, A. R. (2019). Manajemen perpustakaan sekolah dalam merealisasikan pengembangan kurikulum 2013 (kurtilas) di smk wiradikarya ciseeng bogor. *Islamic Management: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 2(01). doi:10.30868/im.v2i01.376
7. Bernardo, M., de Souza, M. A. M., Lopes, R. S. M., & Rodrigues, L. F. (2020). University library performance management: Applying zero-sum gains DEA models to resource allocation. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 100808. doi:10.1016/j.seps.2020.100808
8. De Bem, R. M., Coelho, C. C. d. S. R., & Dandolini, G. A. (2016). Knowledge management framework to the university libraries. *Library Management*. doi:10.1108/LM-01-2016-0005
9. Everett, S. (2018). Visualizing the silent dialogue about race: Diversity outreach in an academic library. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 44(4). doi:10.1016/j.acalib.2018.04.002

10. Fitria, A. (2018). Pemanfaatan perpustakaan sekolah oleh siswa di sekolah dasar negeri golo yogyakarta. *BASIC EDUCATION*, 7(5). Retrieved from <http://journal.student.uny.ac.id/ojs/index.php/pgsd/article/viewFile/10669/10232>.
11. Harisanti, D., & Anugrah, E. P. (2018). Characteristics of senior high school student in the utilization of school library in indonesia. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(3.7). Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a719/8d2a9f86fae3d016ab91746ee6f0bbc7c8ad.pdf>.
12. Harshani, K., Khatibi, A., & Azam, S. F. (2019). Evaluating the effect of academic library users' experience towards library patronage in state universities in sri lanka: development of a conceptual framework. *Global Journal of Management And Business Research*. Retrieved from <https://journalofbusiness.org/index.php/GJMBR/article/view/2987>.
13. Hermawan, W., & Prayoga, A. (2020). Implementasi pengelolaan perpustakaan di madrasah swasta. *MANAZHIM*, 2(1). doi:10.36088/manazhim.v2i1.652
14. Jan, S. U., & Anwar, M. A. (2019). Emotional intelligence, library use and academic achievement of university students. *Journal of the Australian Library and Information Association*, 68(1). doi:10.1080/24750158.2019.1572482
15. Kamulyan, M. S., & Primasari, F. (2016). Implementasi perpustakaan sekolah sebagai sumber belajar dalam meningkatkan prestasi belajar siswa. *Profesi Pendidikan Dasar*, 1(1), 17-30. Retrieved from <http://journals.ums.ac.id/index.php/ppd/article/viewFile/1551/1091>.
16. Karplus, S. S. (2006). Integrating academic library resources and learning management systems: The library Blackboard site. *Education Libraries*, 29(1), 5-11. doi:10.26443/el.v29i1.219
17. Marlina, R., & Suandi, E. (2019). Implementasi manajemen perpustakaan sekolah untuk meningkatkan minat baca dan hasil belajar siswa sma negeri 2 gunung labuhan kabupaten way kanan tahun pelajaran 2014/2015. *jurnal Al-Harokah*, 1(01), 70-76.
18. Masdul, M. R., & Rahmawati, R. (2019). Implementasi manajemen perpustakaan universitas muhammadiyah palu dalam meningkatkan minat baca mahasiswa. *Jurnal Kolaboratif Sains*, 1(1). doi:10.31934/jom.v1i1.852
19. Muspawi, M., & Piana, E. O. (2018). Manajemen Perpustakaan sekolah untuk sumber belajar peserta didik. *Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi*, 18(2). doi:10.33087/jiubj.v18i2.475
20. Novyanti, R., Dahrani, F., Padli, P., & Maharani, S. H. (2019). Manajemen perpustakaan sekolah pada sdn mawar vi banjarmasin. *Jurnal IMPACT: Implementation and Action*, 1(1). doi:10.31961/impact.v1i1.627
21. Omigie, C. A., & Idiedo, O. V. (2019). Developing classroom libraries for promoting primary education in nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/b9601c480c4d307e5d1be68eee197a38/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=54903>.
22. Pors, N. O., & Johannsen, C. G. (2003). Library directors under cross-pressure between new public management and value-based management. *Library Management*. doi:10.1108/01435120310454511
23. Putra, A. E., & Nugroho, A. S. (2019). Manajemen Perpustakaan dalam meningkatkan minat baca peserta didik. *Ta'lim*. Retrieved from <http://www.journal.uml.ac.id/index.php/TL/article/viewFile/114/109>.
24. Putri, M. K., & Maralis, R. (2019). Analisis manajemen sumber daya manusia di perpustakaan sekolah tinggi ilmu ekonomi indragiri (stie-i) rengat kabupaten indragiri hulu. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 8(1). doi:10.34006/jmbi.v8i1.55
25. Raghu, M., & Mothukuri, A. (2017). Best library practices in business schools of Hyderabad: A case study VJIM. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 7(4). Retrieved from <https://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/55718623/205-216.pdf?response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3>.
26. Rokan, M. R. (2017). Manajemen perpustakaan sekolah. *Jurnal Iqra*, 11(01). doi:10.30829/iqra.v11i01.795
27. Saputra, D. F. (2018). Visualisasi data di sistem manajemen perpustakaan. *Jurnal Perpustakaan Pertanian*, 26(2). doi:10.21082/jpp.v26n2.2017.p82-86
28. Siagian, M. D., Siregar, R., & Nasution, E. A. (2019). Optimalisasi penjadwalan dengan analisis jaringan kerja pada kegiatan verifikasi koleksi buku di perpustakaan sekolah. *InfoTekJar: Jurnal Nasional Informatika dan Teknologi Jaringan*, 4(1). Retrieved from <https://jurnal.uisu.ac.id/index.php/infotekjar/article/download/1550/pdf>.
29. Siregar, B. G. (2017). Implementasi manajemen perpustakaan berbasis teknologi untuk percepatan pelayanan. *Al-Kuttab: Jurnal Perpustakaan dan Informasi*, 4(1). Retrieved from

<http://jurnal.iainpadangsidempuan.ac.id/index.php/alkuttab/article/download/619/542>.

30. Suhaemin, S., & Arikunto, S. (2013). Manajemen perpustakaan di madrasah aliyah negeri Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Akuntabilitas Manajemen Pendidikan*, 1(2). doi:10.21831/amp.v1i2.2398
31. Suhardi, D. (2011). Peranan manajemen perpustakaan sekolah dalam mendukung tujuan sekolah. *EduLib*, 1(1). doi:10.17509/edulib.v1i1.1140
32. Swee, T. L., & Abdullah, A. (2005). The status of school library automation in Malaysian Chinese secondary schools: a national survey. *Malaysian Journal of Library & Information Science*, 10(1). Retrieved from <https://jice.um.edu.my/index.php/MJLIS/article/view/8477>.
33. Williment, K. (2019). It takes a community to create a library. *Public Library Quarterly*. doi:10.1080/01616846.2019.1590757
34. Yeh, S.-T., & Walter, Z. (2016). Critical success factors for integrated library system implementation in academic libraries: A qualitative study. *Information Technology and Libraries*, 35(3), 27-42. doi:10.1016/j.seps.2016.09.009
35. Yuliana, C. P., Sri, S. H., & Putra, R. S. (2019). Manajemen kinerja guru pustakawan dalam pemberdayaan perpustakaan sekolah pada sman 2 meulaboh. *LIBRIA*, 11(1). Retrieved from <https://www.jurnal.ar-raniry.ac.id/index.php/libria/article/download/4990/3289>.
36. Zohriah, A. (2018). Manajemen perpustakaan sekolah/madrasah. *Tarbawi: Jurnal Keilmuan Manajemen Pendidikan*, 4(02). doi:10.32678/tarbawi.v4i02.1228

Cite this Article: Alifa Soraya Nuryadika, Hasan Hariri (2021). School Library Management: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 4(2), 127-138